

Ways to teach students to write essays from written work types in elementary grades

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассказывается о том, как познакомить школьников с правилами письма, научить их писать сочинение, правильно писать сочинение на основе осмысленных правил.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативное общение, Эссе, Сюжет, доказательство, тезис, план, тема, орфографические ошибки, эпиграф.

Abstract: This scientific article talks about introducing schoolchildren to the rules of writing, teaching them to write an essay, and writing the essay correctly based on the meaningful rules.

Key words: Communicative communication, Essay, Plot, evidence, thesis, plan, theme, spelling mistakes, epigraph.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada maktab o'quvchilarini yozma ish yozish qoidalari bilan tanishtirish, insho yozishga o'rgatish, inshoni mazmunli qoidalariga asosan to'g'ri yozilishi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kommunikativ muloqot, Insho, Syujet, dalil, tezis, plan, mavzu, imlo xatosiz yozish, epigraf.

The development and future of our country is closely related to quality changes in the field of education, to achieve high efficiency and to what extent their compatibility with the requirements of world education finds its place in

practical activities. remarkable work is being done to find it. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" will increase the demand for education, in particular, for primary education, which forms the basis of the continuous education system, and in particular, for primary education, which forms the basis of the continuous education system. led to a positive change. Primary education mainly consists of the period of inculcating the elements of the basics of literacy in the student's mind. Literacy in this period creates a solid foundation for the intellectual competence of the next stages of the continuous education system. Dear President, according to the event, "If the foundation is provided with solid knowledge and education, it will be easy for the student to master any subject in the upper grades." one of the main goals of lim is aimed at the formation of literacy necessary for general secondary education. Therefore, it is necessary to seriously approach the requirements for the content of education in the training of future teachers.

In the first and second grades, children are prepared for activities in school life. General concepts of academic subjects are given, reading, writing, calculation, observation, and the formation of labor skills, the main attention was paid to the full acquisition of literacy. In the third and fourth grades, knowledge, skills and abilities are further strengthened, initial theoretical concepts and ideas are formed. It is known that man has always been interested in improving his oral and written speech. It is through speech capabilities that a person fully expresses his inner world and feelings. A primary school teacher can use various methods and methods to systematize students' creative speech activities in the practice of literary education. One of the main directions of speech development in reading

classes is the educational analysis of the text, which is carried out by creating various speech situations, creating a situation for dialogic communication, and teaching the use of monologic speech types on literary topics. The criteria for checking the development of students' speech are determined by the possession of active lexicon, terminology, figurative expressions, making the speech meaningful and rich in information, enriching the statements with logical accuracy and independence of conclusions, etc. Today, the level of written and oral speech of young students is not only methodological or pedagogical, but also one of the social problems of society. Most of the participants of the communicative dialogue can clearly and fluently express their opinion, the ability to express their thoughts in a certain system, but it can be observed at all stages of the educational system, in the system of all academic subjects.

In educational practice, mainly in literary education, attention is paid to achieving subtle aspects of expression, its diversity and emotionality. Acquiring such skills and improving oral speech is carried out during conversations, discussions, retellings, dialogues, lectures. In mastering all academic subjects at school, in particular, in primary literary education, works of visual art are referred to from the first grade, based on their purpose. Because in the basic curriculum of the Ministry of Public Education for the 2018-2019 academic year, one hour per week is allocated to fine art lessons starting from the 1st grade of primary education. Therefore, students learn examples of brush art from the first grade of education. In the practice of primary literary education, it is appropriate to read, understand, and analyze the pictures that are the product of brushwork in the same way as literary and artistic works are read and analyzed. Because both in the

artistic text and in the brushwork, the subject is the subject, idea, artistic style, images, symbols, and the period of the event, the characters described in the works of both directions are expressed. elementary school teachers, but also high school teachers, cannot provide accurate information about the creation of works of art, its subject, subject, idea, artistry.

Because in the national higher pedagogical education, future teachers are not taught to read examples of fine art. That is why, regardless of how many lessons and in which class the examples of visual art are used, they are left without getting into their essence and without being analyzed. The reason is that teachers cannot teach their students what they do not know. In the course of literary education of primary grades, the works related to creating oral stories and writing essays based on the content of pictures with various subjects are organized in order to develop students' oral and written speech, of course. Future elementary school teachers will be given some knowledge, even if only briefly, in order to organize fine art classes about it in high school.

While teaching students to write an essay, it is necessary to provide information about the essay and the rules of written speech. Every student should have an idea of the difference between oral and written speech. In oral speech, the speaker achieves easier understanding of his thoughts with hand movements while expressing his opinions. He has the ability to choose the tone according to the content of the speech. When giving information about the essay, it is good to expand the meaning of the word "essay". "Insho" is an Arabic word meaning "to create", "to build", "to build", "to start". In our language, the meaning of this word is much narrower, and it is mainly used in the sense of creative writing written by

students. and a creative text that demonstrates skills and knowledge on this topic is a small work. Just as the writer and poet, scientist and reporter look at the work, scientific work, article they write with great responsibility, the student should prepare for it in every way before writing an essay. Because the essay is a reflection of the student's spirituality and wisdom. It reflects the student's knowledge, feelings, and skills to express their thoughts.

There are basically 3 types of essays: Literary essay, Literary-creative essay, Free essay. Simple written images familiar to us from the first grade, stories based on pictures, and various letters are also similar to essays. But they cannot be called essays in the literal sense. Because in such written work, the student's independence and creativity are limited. 1. Essays on literary topics include topics explained by the teacher in class and noted in literature lessons. 2. Writing essays on literary and creative topics, on the one hand, as a separate topic in the lesson obtained information, on the other hand, outside the classroom, the student is required to think about the materials acquired. When writing essays of the first type, the student's independent thinking is relatively limited. But this consideration should not lead to the conclusion that they do not require independent thinking. In the second type of essays, the student's independence is felt more vividly. Because the student's attitude to the topic is of primary importance when writing them. 3. Free essays are written on topics that are not directly mentioned in literature classes. Students are free to write on whatever topics they like. For example: Dreams, career choice, Homeland and other topics can be covered. Students should master the meaning of terms such as topic, plan, epigraph, thesis, argument while developing the skills of writing an essay.

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